

ABOUT THE RESEARCH OF TOPONYMS OF TURKISH ORIGIN

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Abstract

As is clear, certain regularities are evident in the transition of common words and vocabulary units to onomastic units. In order to determine these regularities, first of all, the toponymy system of linguistically related peoples should be investigated in a comparative manner. From this point of view, the discovery of similarities and differences between toponyms in the area inhabited by Turkic peoples can greatly help to reveal the typological aspects of toponyms. Toponyms of Azerbaijan and Turkey also have common typological features that are manifested in the creation of toponyms and onomastic units belonging to most nations, and it is natural that such features are much more common in toponyms of Turkish origin than in non-Turkish toponyms. One close aspect of the toponyms in the territory of Turkey and Azerbaijan is that the defining words, geographical terms, personal names and their frequency of use are the same and similar.

West Azerbaijan is an unforgettable part of our history. A piece of heart, a piece of heaven. In these lands, Dede Gorgud played the gong, added words, gave names to the brave, Koroglu showed his strength to the old enemy, Ashiq Alasgar praised our mountains, ice springs, and our land with flowers. The land of Western Azerbaijan has given Azerbaijan science outstanding people - public figures, people who have their say in the world of science, culture, literature and art. The geographical environment of "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud" saga is also related to Western Azerbaijan. Shirokuvan, Altuntakht, and Goycha lakes mentioned in the epic were the homelands of Oghuz heroes and these areas are now located within the territory of Western Azerbaijan. The indigenous inhabitants of Western Azerbaijan were Azerbaijani Turks. It is the result of this that historically, that is, until 1991, more than 90 percent of the toponyms of the area were words of Turkish origin.

Keywords: toponyms, clan, tribe, Turkic peoples, ethnic groups.

Such studies are also important in determining which language the toponyms in a certain area are based on, which language is based on vocabulary units, in other words, which peoples they belong to. This, in turn, can be of great help in revealing the history of settlement and migration direction of Turkish tribes and tribes in that area.

In terms of learning the history of the Azerbaijani language (and Turkic languages in general) and the history of the Turkic peoples, the comparative study of toponyms is undoubtedly beneficial. Carrying out this kind of comparison on the toponyms created by Turkish and Azerbaijani Turks, who are neighbors in terms of geographical area, or formed from the same ethnic groups (tribes and tribes), in our opinion, may allow us to obtain more necessary scientific results. [2, 15-18]

In this article, we tried to compare the toponyms of Azerbaijan and Turkey. A preliminary observation of the toponyms of these two countries allows us to come to the following preliminary conclusions:

Toponyms of Azerbaijan and Turkey also have common typological features that are manifested in the creation of toponyms and onomastic units belonging to most nations, and it is natural that such features are much more common in toponyms of Turkish origin than in non-Turkish toponyms.

A large number of toponyms in both countries have a common Turkic character. To one degree or another, they are also found in the area inhabited by other Turkic peoples. For example: Saray, Kangli (Kanli), Abdaloba, Abdalli Madrasa, Madrasa, Garadag (Karadag, Kangir), Kangarli, Agdash, Akdash, etc. [6, 88-91]

Most of the similar and identical toponyms we have shown are, of course, in the territory of Azerbaijan and Turkey. Our goal is to talk in detail about the toponyms we include in this group. First of all, it should be noted that a large number of toponyms common to Azerbaijan and Turkey are repeated many times either in both countries or in one of them. For example: Karaman (Karamanli), Shamli, Karagoyunlu, Agdam, Saatli, Kechili, Bayat, Yayci, Bashkend//Başköy, Yenikend//Tazakend//Yenikoy, Karalar, Chamurlu, Gozlu, Hacilar, Khalaj, Qamishli, Kizilca, Kosalar, Karabakh, etc.

The toponyms that we include in the third group are different according to the degree of similarity. In this respect, they can be grouped as follows:

1. Those who are exactly the same. Azerbaijani toponyms, which are identical and generally similar to their counterparts in Turkey, are of course not only in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, but also in most places where Azerbaijani Turks live, especially in the territories of West Azerbaijan, Georgia, South Azerbaijan and Dagestan. [3, 21]

They are the majority in the territory of South Azerbaijan, Georgia, West Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan bordering with Turkey. For example: Ince, Bagil, Gerkar, Hacilar, Sarvan, Goynuk, Yengija//Yenija, Tatarli, Chamli, Goyceli, Afshar//Avshar, Ojagli, Derbend, Karasu, Tazakend, Yenikand, Sadakhli, Giziltep, Dadeli, Amasiya, Ilisu, Kyzylja//Kyzylca, Eymur, Goylar, Kosalar, Kirygli, Karalar, Alibeyli, Garahajili, Alpout, Sarigamysh//Sarikamish, Oxchuoglu//Okchuoglu, Gizilveng//Kyzylveng, Colakhli, Karabakh//Karabagh, Chardakhli, Atabay, Gazanchi//Kazanchi, Ulash, Soful, etc.

2. A certain part of the toponyms common to both states differ from each other to one degree or another in terms of the presence of toponyms and geographical terms. There are several types of them:

a) Most of the geographical terms in Azerbaijan and Turkey have the same words - mountain, river, valley, hill, etc. if it is expressed, the other part of them is indicated by different words: village//koy, spring//spring//paya//, palace//bed//home, desert//yazi, plain, etc.

b) Toponyms involved in the creation of toponyms of Azerbaijan and Turkey are identical. However, some differences are evident in the development of these toponyms. For example: Arabkir//Arapgir, Jil//Jilli, Daşlı//Staşlı etc. [4, 39]

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President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, who always attaches great importance to restoring our historical memory and preserving it to future generations, said on December 24 while getting acquainted with the conditions created in the administrative building of the West Azerbaijan Community: "West Azerbaijan is our historical land, this is confirmed by many historical documents, historical maps, our history confirms it.[3, 44]

99 percent of the names of mountains, rivers, steppes, forests, plains, villages are of Turkish origin. It is known that the names of mountains and rivers originated before settlements. This is a fact that proves that our grandfathers settled in these areas in earlier times. It is clear from the map that this is an area belonging to Azerbaijanis.

It should be noted that one of the tribes that had a settlement during the time of the Garagoyunlu state, and whose inhabitants contributed a lot to the establishment of this state, were the Barana people. The Barana people, a very old Turkic branch, lived in Western Azerbaijan. Once upon a time there was a large district named after the Barana tribe. Thus, Barana district was a very famous district in Western Azerbaijan.

Goycha district, which has an unparalleled place in the history of Azerbaijan, is one of our ancestral

lands, covering a wide area along the shores of Goycha Lake. This area was part of the Iravan Khanate and later Iravan Governorate until it was annexed to the Russian Empire by war. During the Soviet rule, Goyche district was artificially divided into five administrative districts. They are Chambarak, Basarkechar, Ashagi Garanlig, Kavar and Yelenovka districts.

Goycha district is famous as one of the homelands of Azerbaijani folklore and ashig art. This district is rich in toponyms of Turkish origin. Although most of those toponyms have been changed, their names live in fiction and memories.

By the way, we should also mention one issue that we had valuable scientists who devoted a lot of work to researching the toponyms and historical past of Azerbaijan, either in the former Soviet era or in the years of independence. One of our scientists was Hasan Mirzayev, doctor of philology, professor, Honored Scientist, better known as a philologist-scientist in the Azerbaijan Linguistic School. More than 250 pages of his 540-page book "Azerbaijan toponyms and dialect words" are dedicated to the toponyms of Deraleyaz district, which covers the toponymy of the region as a whole and gives the reader a complete and clear idea of the oikonymy, ethnonymy, oronymy, and hydronymy of the area.

At this point, we should also remember that the toponyms of Western Azerbaijan have been restored on the "GoMap.az" electronic platform. And the names of all changed cultural and historical monuments are now displayed with their historical names in Azerbaijani language.

What the head of the country said in a meeting with a group of intellectuals from Western Azerbaijan: "Western Azerbaijanis are a community that has been illegally deported many times. Their rights must be restored and they must return to their native lands", we want to emphasize once again that the time will come when the names of places and countries, which are the memory of Azerbaijan's lands and become their passports, will regain the right to citizenship.

Aghbaba, Aghbud, Aghbulag, Aghweis, Aghdaban, etc. in the section "Lexical-semantic features of paleotoponyms with the "white" component, Alavar, Alakuk, Alakilsa, Alagoz, Alapapax, Alapars, etc., in the section "Lexical-semantic features of toponyms with a black" component, Gararaxhac, Garabulag, Garaveng, Garadag, etc., in the section "Shades of meaning of the word "yellow" in the toponymic system of Western Azerbaijan" toponyms Sariyokhush, Sariyal, Saritepe, Sarijalar, in the section "Linguistic features of the process of changing the ancient phonetic and lexical-semantic levels of toponyms" Moz, Mozkand, Mozannene, Shorca, Chiva, etc. toponyms were involved in linguistic-etymological analysis.[3, 118-121]

A.Başkan, Doğan, Aksan M. Dođru and other Turkish researchers have provided a statistical analysis of geographical terms, adjectives, numbers, pronouns, adverbs and personal names (anthroponyms) involved in the creation of toponyms in Turkey, and identified the most effective ones.

When the toponyms of Azerbaijan are grouped by that method and compared with the corresponding toponyms of Turkey, it becomes clear that the frequency of their use is very close and similar to each other. [2, 113-114]

It is known that the names in the system of toponyms of Azerbaijan are not the same according to their language affiliation and distribution areas, and the units involved in their creation and derivation are also not homogeneous in origin.

In this process, words of Turkish (Azerbaijani) origin had a leading and decisive position, and although they do not constitute the majority, there are also toponyms formed from borrowings of languages historically connected with the Azerbaijani language and lexical units of other languages existing in this area. From this point of view, names of Turkish (Azerbaijani) origin in Azerbaijani toponymy form its main mass, core, core, main background and fund.

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